

AI-GeoSpecies

Training & capacity building resources

Cos4Cloud Services

About the AI-GeoSpecies system and user guide

This is a system and user guide to [AI-GeoSpecies](#), a Cos4Cloud service that uses artificial intelligence to predict which species users can observe in a particular area.

Description

This is a system and user guide to **AI-GeoSpecies**, a Cos4Cloud service that uses artificial intelligence (AI) to predict which species users can find in a particular area. Web-based it shows a wide range of biodiversity data (i.e. plant species) from a geographical area. Future plans are to include environmental variables i.e. temperature, precipitation, soil type, groundcover, distance from water, species, etc. from several different sources.

AI-GeoSpecies has been developed by [Inria](#) as part of [Cos4Cloud](#) a European Horizon 2020 funded project. The Cos4Cloud project has developed [thirteen services](#) boosting citizen science technological services to help increase and improve the quantity and quality of observations.

This is one of the Cos4Cloud services developed by [Inria](#), for existing and new citizen science initiatives providing artificial intelligence (AI)-based Species Photo ID and AI-based Biodiversity Prediction as tools and resources for biodiversity. Inria is one of the research organisations behind [Pl@ntNet](#) - a citizen observatory with an extensive database that uses AI to help people identify and better understand plants.

Service Coordinator

Cos4Cloud Coordinator

The following content has been provided to help guide users of this service.

WHAT IS AI-GEOSPECIES

AI-GeoSpecies is a location-based prediction web service that uses artificial intelligence to show possible plant species that can be observed in a set area. Users select a location to a precise geographical area (geo-coordinates) and the system shows a list of the possible plant species that are most likely to be observed in this area.

WHO IS THIS SERVICE FOR?

AI-GeoSpecies is targeted at developers with some experience in web technologies, it can be integrated into citizen science applications, citizen observatory websites or platforms etc., or by any organisation developing a citizen observatory app to collect biodiversity data. It shows users the species likely to be observed in a particular area for example, a developer of a gamified citizen science app will be able to suggest the species to be observed at a given location.

Developed as a web service, **AI-GeoSpecies** can be integrated into applications (Apps) but is not an app itself.

As a demonstration, it has been integrated as the [GeoPl@ntNet](#) web application, powered by [Pl@ntNet](#) which is accessible to anyone interested in trialling the service.

WHAT ARE THE BENEFITS OF THIS SERVICE?

AI-GeoSpecies is a service that can be integrated into new or existing citizen science apps or citizen observatory platforms. It provides potential innovation for citizen observatories to automatically predict a list of species that are most likely to be observed at a given location. It is not usually possible to learn species distribution models (SDM) directly from available spatial positions because of the limited number of occurrences and the sampling bias.

AI-GeoSpecies meets this challenge. It is a technology that can be of benefit or have many potential practical uses for biodiversity conservation, citizen science, sustainable management of natural and urban areas, environmental education, ecotourism, etc. It can be used to view up to 4,000 plant species at a time and adapted to one-off queries or specific small-scale areas (e.g. a few kilometres). However, it is not a mapping tool, therefore a citizen science user, for example, would not be able to directly see a map with species spots and names.

Future possible benefits and uses

In addition to biodiversity, i.e. plant species, **AI-GeoSpecies** has the potential to use big data and deep-learning techniques to train a large-scale predictive model that can show environmental data such as temperature, precipitation, soil type, groundcover, distance from water, species, etc. This would involve the development of an information system aggregating data from several sources i.e. [Global Biodiversity Information Facility \(GBIF\)](#) on species occurrences; [KNMI Climate Explorer](#) to investigate climate data; [Copernicus Earth Observation data](#) i.e. Corine Land Cover data, satellite imagery data, etc.

HOW DOES IT WORK?

AI-GeoSpecies is a web service that shows potential plant species to be observed in a set area. It uses a prediction model that considers a large list of species in a geographic area currently on a scale of four thousand plant species. It can find out the probability of observing a species in a particular area

The service provides information about the *probability of finding 'X' species at a particular location*. It will also allow for the integration of *warning messages* based on the probability of observing some particular species.

AI-GeoSpecies also has the potential to provide notifications of the presence of exotic or endangered species through the integration of warning messages conditioned by the probability of observing some particular species (e.g. to signal the presence of invasive or endangered species).

HOW TO USE AI-GEOSPECIES – A STEP BY STEP GUIDE

AI-GeoSpecies can be used in two ways:

- Access the service using the demonstration developed which is directly linked too *Pl@ntNet* using: [GeoPl@ntNet](#)
- Developers can integrate the service directly into Apps, citizen observatories etc. using the information provided

AI-GEOSPECIES ON PL@NTNET: GEOPL@NTNET

01

Test the **AI-GeoSpecies** using *GeoPl@ntNet*: Go to: <https://identify.plantnet.org/prediction>: Select a rectangular area on the map (as small or large as required)

02

Click 'Search', the service returns a list of plant species that can be found in the selected area:

03

For each species, the system also returns the number of known occurrences of the species in the selected area (if any) by querying the GBIF portal API:

04

The data generated can be exported, downloaded and saved as a CSV file:

INTEGRATING AI-GEOSPECIES: GEOLOCATION BASED SPECIES PREDICTION

01

To integrate AI-GeoSpecies into a citizen observatory etc.: Go to: <https://my-api.plantnet.org/#/partners/getV2PredictionGeoSpecies> to access the JSON-based REST service:

02

To implement, request a *Pl@ntNet* API Key at: <https://my.plantnet.org/>.

03

Click 'Try it out' enter this and other parameters, here: <https://my-api.plantnet.org/#/partners/getV2PredictionGeoSpecies> and 'Execute'.

Parameters Try it out

Name	Description
lang string (query)	two-letter ISO 639-1 language code Available values : en, fr, es, pt, de, it, ar, cs, nl, sk, zh, ru, tr, pl, uk, he, el, fi, id, ms, ca, ja, hu, hr, da, ro, bg, nb, sl, sv, et, eu, ur, ml, cy, ku, gl Default value : en <input type="text" value="en"/>
topLeftLon * <small>required</small> number (query)	Longitude (WGS 84 decimal degrees) <input type="text" value="topLeftLon"/>
topLeftLat * <small>required</small> number (query)	Latitude (WGS 84 decimal degrees) <input type="text" value="topLeftLat"/>
bottomRightLon * <small>required</small> number (query)	Longitude (WGS 84 decimal degrees) <input type="text" value="bottomRightLon"/>
bottomRightLat * <small>required</small> number (query)	Latitude (WGS 84 decimal degrees) <input type="text" value="bottomRightLat"/>
api-key string (query)	Your private API key <input type="text" value="api-key"/>
authnix-access-token string (query)	Authnix access token <input type="text" value="authnix-access-token"/>

Parameters Cancel

Name	Description
lang string (query)	two-letter ISO 639-1 language code Available values : en, fr, es, pt, de, it, ar, cs, nl, sk, zh, ru, tr, pl, uk, he, el, fi, id, ms, ca, ja, hu, hr, da, ro, bg, nb, sl, sv, et, eu, ur, ml, cy, ku, gl Default value : en <input type="text" value="en"/>
topLeftLon * <small>required</small> number (query)	Longitude (WGS 84 decimal degrees) <input type="text" value="topLeftLon"/>
topLeftLat * <small>required</small> number (query)	Latitude (WGS 84 decimal degrees) <input type="text" value="topLeftLat"/>
bottomRightLon * <small>required</small> number (query)	Longitude (WGS 84 decimal degrees) <input type="text" value="bottomRightLon"/>
bottomRightLat * <small>required</small> number (query)	Latitude (WGS 84 decimal degrees) <input type="text" value="bottomRightLat"/>
api-key string (query)	Your private API key <input type="text" value="api-key"/>
authnix-access-token string (query)	Authnix access token <input type="text" value="authnix-access-token"/>

Execute

04

The response results will be generated:

Responses Response content type application/json

Code	Description
200	Successful

Example value Model

```
{
  "name": "string",
  "author": "string",
  "family": "string",
  "genus": {
    "id": "string"
  },
  "loc": {
    "commitment": [
      "string"
    ]
  },
  "images": [
    {
      "id": "string",
      "url": "string",
      "s": "string"
    }
  ],
  "observationsCount": 0,
  "prediction": {
    "source": "string",
    "score": 0
  }
}
```


INFORMATION AND FURTHER SUPPORT

Introduction to this Cos4Cloud service: <https://cos4cloud-eosc.eu/services/ai-geo-species/>

AI-GeoSpecies online – try the GeoPl@ntNet demo: <https://identify.plantnet.org/prediction>

AI- GeoSpecies contact: api@plantnet-project.org

Access the API: <https://my-api.plantnet.org/#/partners/getV2PredictionGeoSpecies>

AI-GeoSpecies online – try the Pl@ntNet demo: <https://identify.plantnet.org/prediction>

AI GeoSpecies contact: api@plantnet-project.org

Access the API: <https://my-api.plantnet.org/#/partners/getV2PredictionGeoSpecies>

API documentation can be found here: <https://my.plantnet.org/doc/openapi>

Pl@ntNet API FAQs: <https://my.plantnet.org/doc/faq>

About Pl@ntNet: <https://plantnet.org/en/>

Get the Cos4Cloud infographic for this service: [AI-GeoSpecies infographic](#)

Additional resources: [About the Cos4Cloud Toolbox and Evidence Hub](#)

This system and user guide is a training resource for AI-GeoSpecies, one of the technological services co-designed by the Cos4Cloud project (<https://cos4cloud-eosc.eu/>). **Title: AI-GeoSpecies System and User Guide.** Service Coordinator Inria. This guide is one of the Training and Capacity Building resources in the Cos4Cloud Toolbox & Evidence Hub developed by the Open University in collaboration with project partners. Contact: cos4cloud-toolbox@open.ac.uk.

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